

How to conduct degradation simulations with a target mass loss using **tml-wei.py**

The present code aims to simulate the corrosion process using the finite element method and analyses the resulting concentration data. It was originally developed by Danny Mangels and later extended by Alan Malky to increase its flexibility and circumvent the need for Abaqus CAE. The purpose of the code is to simulate corrosion processes on components by mass diffusion analyses analysing parameters such as mass loss, relative density, and damage degrees within an automated workflow. The Weibull distribution is used to include local pitting corrosion attacks and statistical effects. Fluxes on the surface of a component are prescribed, and iterations are continuously performed until a desired level of mass loss (target mass loss, tml) is reached.

The code reads data from ODB file (Output Database from Abaqus) and the input-file (*.inp) to identify the relevant nodes and elements and to adjust the corresponding flux values. A master file needs to be supplied including the complete description of the diffusion problem. This allows for a detailed analysis of the corrosion progress over a defined period under varying conditions. Simultaneously, the code stores essential field data and calculates parameters that can be used for further development and refinement of corrosion process modelling or a follow-up mechanical analysis.

Here are the main goals and functions of the code:

- Extraction of nodes and elements:
- `extract_nodes(mod_name)`: This function reads an input file (.inp) and extracts the nodes that belong to the corrosion surface.
- `extract_elements(odb_datei)`: This function opens an ODB file and extracts the elements that belong to the corrosion volume.

Simulation settings and parameters:

- The code defines various parameters for the simulation, such as target mass loss, Weibull distribution parameters, corrosion time and steps, initial concentration and other relevant parameters.

Weibull distribution:

- The code creates or reads a Weibull distribution, which is used to distribute the flow values across the outer surface nodes.

Manipulation of the input file:

- The code copies the contents of the original input file to a new working file and adjusts the Weibull distributed values to achieve the prescribed total flow value.

Features:

- The procedure works for any 3D part
- It is based on a finite-element mass diffusion analysis
- An ABAQUS master input-file has to be provided
- Surfaces attacked by corrosion need to be specified in the model
- The volume considered for the calculation of the mass loss must be defined independently from the surfaces
- The step definitions define the timescale (in seconds!)
- The (global) target mass loss needs to be prescribed in a python code together with the parameter (α) describing the Weibull distribution of fluxes on the surface
- The Weibull parameter A regulates the localisation of corrosion ($\alpha \rightarrow \infty$: homogeneous corrosion; $\alpha \rightarrow 0$: localised corrosion)
- The code iteratively runs simulations, calculates the mass loss at the end of the step and compares this value with the prescribed one. The overall flux is then adjusted until the target mass loss is met
- On demand, several helpful files are written, such as the (final) nodal fluxes used, the 3D-field of damage caused by the corrosion and the initial conditions in terms of damage for subsequent mechanical analyses
- To run the python code, a respective ABAQUS Standard license is required, but no CAE license is needed.

Code of conduct and user agreement

The software falls into *application class 1* defined in "Guideline for the development and distribution of software" of the Helmholtz Centre Hereon. Please adhere to our Code of Conduct to ensure a welcoming and inclusive environment for all contributors.

The software is developed exclusively for use within Hereon. (inner source policy) It is designed to be utilized and modified by Hereon employees to meet internal needs and enhance operational efficiency. However, it is strictly prohibited to share, distribute, or disclose this software, in whole or in part, to any third parties outside the company. Unauthorized sharing or distribution may result in disciplinary action and potential legal consequences.

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How to Contribute

If you encounter any bugs or have suggestions for improvements, please send us an Email or call. Provide as much detail as possible to help us understand and address the problem. If you need any help or have questions, feel free to reach out to the authors of this document.

Description of the ABAQUS master input file

The following figures show the definition of corrosion surface and volume. They have to be named CORROSIONSURFACE and CORROSIONVOLUME, respectively. The script works in the way that these "sets" need to be defined on the level of the part. Respective node sets and element sets are generated automatically once the definition is given on the part in Abaqus CAE. In case the definition is done manually, note that the surface nodes are used to apply the fluxes, and the element set is used to calculate the mass loss. Note that names of the instance matter, in the example it is INST_TORSION3D. Moreover, note that the corrosion volume does not need to be identical with the volume wrapped by the corrosion surface.

Corrosion surface definition

Corrosion volume definition

For the mass diffusion analysis, material definition must be provided in terms of diffusivity, concentration of matter (here: magnesium fading out of the alloy) and solubility. The following values seem to do the job:

```
*Diffusivity
1.0e-07, 6.736e-05
*Solubility
1.0
```

A definition of mechanical characteristics is not required.

The step definition

A transient mass diffusion analysis will be performed. The definition of two steps is required: the assignment step of the initial concentration to all elements in the model, and the diffusion process over the time (given in seconds – consistent dimensions!). While the time of the first step is physically irrelevant, the second step must capture the physical corrosion time. This is taken care of by the script, the respective line in the master-input file will be replaced. To make this possible, the first entry (initial time increment) should be 12345.

Specify the field quantities CONC and IVOL as the field output, since the mass loss is calculated on this basis.

```
*Step, name=c-assignment, nlgeom=NO
```

```

*Mass Diffusion, end=SS, dcmx=1e-07
0.01, 1., 1e-05, 1., 1e-06
** Name: assignment Type: Mass concentration
*Boundary
inst_torsion3D.sample, 11, 11, 6.736e-05

...

*Step, name=corrosion, nlgeom=NO, inc=1000
*Mass Diffusion, end=PERIOD, dcmx=0.05
12345., 3.024e+06, 10., 100000.,

```

The parameter `dcmx` controls the increment size. It might need to be adjusted once the solution appears not physical or takes too many increments. It has its connection with the diffusivity and the magnitude of the nodal fluxes applied, hence a careful assessment of this quantity is recommended.

FE-discretisation

No specific meshing laws need to be followed. The mass diffusion analysis can use tetrahedra (DC3D4, DC3D10), prisms (DC3D6, DC3D15) and bricks (DC3D8, DC3D20). Since node-based fluxes are used in the following, regions of high nodal density (i.e. fine mesh) will cause high concentration changes. Hence, it is recommended to use a regular mesh, with only moderate refinements. A typical mesh is shown below.

Typical mesh (DC3D20)

Setup for the python file (tml-wei.py) controlling the iterative procedure

In the python code several settings are prescribed. Among them, the file names which are read and written in a run:

- name of the master *.inp-file
- name of the simulation series to be done (*.inp, *.odb, etc.)
- name of the text files (*.txt) for saving the data (convergence behaviour bJml and global flux)
- name of the file to read an existing Weibull distribution (case `weil=True`)

- name of the relative density field for the damage parameters (saves node number and relative density)
- name of the damage field (saves nodes coordinates and damage parameter $f=1-\text{rel_d}$)

The physical parameters:

- target mass loss in percent
- parameter A for the Weibull distribution
- step time in days for the corrosion process
- corrosion time in days
- initial density/mass concentration of the material
- concentration ratio at which the mass loss calculation is cut off
- target time step in days (meaning what mass loss shall be achieved after what time in days). Commonly equal `corr_time`.
- allowed divergence in the target mass loss, relevant for the iteration

Switches to create or omit data files

- `bJml=True/False` tracks the prefactor of the Weibull distribution, the overall flux and the current mass loss for every iteration step
- `weis=True/False` enables to save the Weibull distribution of this simulation. This is required in the case a variation of assignments will be conducted afterwards (shuffle, see below). The name of the file is hardwired to `dat_name-weibull.txt`
- `nsum=True/False` tracks the summation of the amount of substance for negative concentrations. The respective value is reported in the file `dat_name.txt`.
- `rdff= True/False` creates a list with nodes and their respective relative density depending on the mass concentration (node-based output used for *INITIAL CONDITION)
- `daff= True/False` creates a list with node coordinates and their respective damage parameter calculated from the relative density ($f=1-\text{rel_d}$)

Switches to toggle on additional features

`weil= True/False` reads an existing Weibull distribution from file (if True)

`shuf= True/False` reassigns an existing Weibull distribution to the nodes (meaningful for analysing statistics). The actual value for tml is reported in the *.bJml-file. Iterations are not executed.

Execution

Provided that the master-file is existing, the iterative procedure will be started by typing

```
nohup abaqus python tml-wei.py &
```

The *.bjml-file can be tailed since it monitors the convergence process by showing the current mass loss as a function of the (global) flux applied. After convergence was achieved, one need to (manually) re-run the problem since the *.inp file includes the final values of fluxes. This should be identical to the last temp.* run.

Examples

The code has been used and tested three times so far based on its present version.

In 2023, the use was restricted to plane surfaces (© Danny Mangels)– results on a target mass loss of 5% are reported in. *Steglich D. et al. Strength and ductility loss of Magnesium-Gadolinium due to corrosion in physiological environment: Experiments and modeling. Journal of the Mechanical Behavior of Biomedical Materials. 2023:105939.* Besides the straight-forward use, the shuffle-functionality was used, see Fig. 13.

In 2024, the functionalities were extended towards economical handling (abaqus python instead of CAE python, © Alan Malky). Further, the definition of corrosion surface and corrosion volume were shifted to the master input file to be more flexible. These features were tested on a round tensile bar, with corrosion attacks present only along the parallel length. Results in terms of concentration for three different Weibull parameters and a global mass loss of 9% are shown below.

3D-sample with different statistical distributions of fluxes, each leading to 9% mass loss: $A=2$, $A=0.4$ and $A=0.05$ (from left to right)

The shuffle feature is designed for reading an existing Weibull distribution of nodal fluxes from a text file, and re-assigning fluxes on nodes. By this, the corrosion pattern appears different. Depending on the problem, the calculated mass loss may be slightly different from the one of the starting problem.

Three variants of one Weibull distribution generated using the “shuffle” function, leading to global mass losses of 8.98, 9.985 and 8.99 %

In late 2024, the code was used to simulate the degradation of a bone screw (dens axis). The respective geometry was provided by Tricumed®. Since the structure includes several constructive details, a fine discretisation using linear tetrahedra was used. Due to the very high number of elements (more than 1.5 Mio), the evaluation of the global mass loss takes approx. 2 days for each iteration. The calculated field of relative densities was read from the file *rdf* for the follow-up mechanical analysis based on progressive damage and failure of the screw.

Dens axis screw, from top to bottom: initial geometry, result of the simulated corrosion (5% mass loss after 5 weeks, $A=0.05$) and contours of constant plastic strain after tensile loading